

Supplementary Information 1

Fig 1. Bivariate plots of predictors spanning the environmental space in the model training extent (in black), overlaid with presence points (in red) of *Hoplobatrachus tigerinus*. Predictors include mean precipitation of the wettest quarter (bio16), maximum temperature of the warmest month (bio5), minimum temperature of the coldest month (bio6) and Human Influence Index (HII).

Fig 2. Ordination diagram, based on a principal component analysis, of the environmental space at *Hoplobatrachus tigerinus* presence points in the native range of the Indian sub-continent (grey), and two introduced range populations on the Andaman Islands (purple) and Madagascar (yellow). Environmental predictors include mean precipitation of the wettest quarter (bio16), maximum temperature of the warmest month (bio5), minimum temperature of the coldest month (bio6), and Human Influence Index (HII). Ellipses drawn with 95% confidence intervals.

Table 1. Spatially-subset k-fold cross validation of ensemble model built with the chosen environmental predictors and four model algorithms, to predict *Hoplobatrachus tigrinus* occurrence in the native range. Environmental predictors include mean precipitation of the wettest quarter (bio16), maximum temperature of the warmest month (bio5), minimum temperature of the coldest month (bio6), and Human Influence Index (HII). Transferability tested by geographically splitting the presence and pseudoabsence data into four quadrants, with three quadrants used to train the model and the fourth quadrant used to test the model with the Boyce index (range 0 to 1); process repeated for all four combination of training-evaluation quadrants (123-4, 234-1, 341-2, and 412-3), across three randomly generated set of pseudoabsences (R1, R2, and R3). Values indicate Boyce index for the ensemble model reflecting the median of model algorithms.

Quadrants	R1	R2	R3
123-4	0.58	0.75	0.72
234-1	0.92	0.84	0.90
341-2	0.76	0.65	0.61
412-3	0.34	0.40	0.36

Fig. 3 Spatially-subset k-fold cross validation of the ensemble model built to predict *Hoplobatrachus tigerinus* occurrence in the native range. Example maps of geographically splitting a) the pseudoabsence data and b) presence data into four quadrants, with three quadrants used to train the model and the fourth quadrant used to test the model.

a)

b)

Fig 4. a) Area Under the receiver operating characteristic Curve (AUC; range from 0 to 1), and b) True Skill Statistic (TSS; range from -1 to 1), of four model algorithms run to predict *Hoplobatrachus tigrinus* habitat suitability in the training extent. The algorithms are the ones selected for the ensemble model: Generalized Linear Model (GLM), Generalized Additive Model (GAM), Classification Tree Analysis (CTA) and Generalized Boosting Model (GBM).

a)

b)

Fig 5. Example response curves of four model algorithms: Generalized Linear Model (GLM, in black), Generalized Additive Model (GAM, in blue), Classification Tree Analysis (CTA, in red), and Generalized Boosting Model, (GBM, in green) depicting the relationship between environmental predictors and *Hoplobatrachus tigerinus* predicted habitat suitability. Environmental predictors include mean precipitation of the wettest quarter (bio16), maximum temperature of the warmest month (bio5), minimum temperature of the coldest month (bio6), and Human Influence Index (hii_wgs resampled).

Fig 6. Model extrapolation maps of predicted suitability for *Hoplobatrachus tigerinus* a) globally, b) in the native range (Indian subcontinent), and the confirmed invaded areas of c) Madagascar and d) Andaman archipelago , based on ensemble ecological niche modelling. Extrapolation values (0 to 4), denote how many predictors fall outside the training value range. Predictor variables included maximum temperature of the warmest month (bio5), minimum temperature of the coldest month (bio6), mean rainfall of the wettest quarter (bio16), and human influence index (HII).

a)

b)

c)

d)

Fig 7. Coefficient of variation maps of predicted suitability for *Hoplobatrachus tigerinus* a) globally, b) in the native range (Indian subcontinent), and the confirmed invaded areas of c) Madagascar and d) Andaman archipelago, based on ensemble ecological niche modelling. Higher values on the legend indicate higher variation across all model runs of the algorithms (Generalized Linear Model, Generalized Additive Model, Classification Tree Analysis, and Generalized Boosting Model). Predictor variables included maximum temperature of the warmest month (bio5), minimum temperature of the coldest month (bio6), mean rainfall of the wettest quarter (bio16), and human influence index (HII).

a)

b)

c)

d)

